

Sensitivity Analysis of Tolerances which Restrict Multiple Similar Features

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Abstract

In tolerancing, the product quality has to be ensured in the presence of geometric variations of the product components. Therefore, tolerances restrict these geometric variations. Usually, functional key characteristics (FKC) are defined, most of them are geometric characteristics of the product. The required product quality then is ensured through requirements of the FKCs. Afterwards, geometric analyses of the FKC variations are performed employing tolerance simulations. These simulations have input parameters (geometric deviation parameters) and output parameters (FKC deviation parameters). To support the product developer in specifying suitable tolerances, sensitivity measures can quantify the impact of single tolerances with respect to a FKC (Ziegler and Wartzack, 2014). A common sensitivity analysis method bases on the conditional variance of the simulation output, which can be calculated by a number of different algorithms (Saltelli, et al, 2008).

Normally, a “tolerance object” is applied on one feature. In some cases, tolerances can restrict multiple geometry elements. In this case, multiple sensitivity values for the geometry elements are calculated by standard sensitivity analysis. This is disadvantageous if the influence of the tolerance which restricts the geometry elements is of interest, because the sensitivity values cannot be simply added together. This paper discusses the case, when a position tolerance is adopted on multiple similar geometry elements. A statistical sampling method for the sensitivity analysis algorithms is introduced. The method is adopted to a hole pattern to show its practical use.

1. Introduction

According to the axiom of manufacturing imprecisions (Srinivasan, 2003) “*all manufacturing processes are inherently imprecise and produce parts that vary*”. These variations can negatively influence the functions of the manufactured product. To avoid this, tolerances restrict these variations. Furthermore, tolerance management is the process of systematically analysing and specifying the tolerances with respect to the product functions. For this purpose, tolerance simulations support the tolerance expert by estimating the impact of geometric variations on the products functions.

As strict tolerances have an high impact on the product costs, it is very important to specify tolerances carefully. For specifying suitable tolerances, tolerance simulations consist of two

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different output quantities: First, the fulfilment of FKC-requirements is estimated. This can be done with worst-case methods (requirements fulfilled/not fulfilled) or with statistical methods (statistical process parameters, probability density estimations of critical dimensions, estimating the inappropriate parts per million, etc.). Second, sensitivity analysis is performed which characterises the influence of single tolerances on the fulfilment of requirements. Sensitivity analysis is a widely used method for analysing simulations in engineering.

2. Sensitivity Analysis

According to Saltelli, et al, (2000), "*sensitivity analysis studies the relationships between information flowing in and out of the model*". This generic definition is chosen here, because the influence of the model input parameters can be calculated with respect to different properties of the model output. There exists a wide variety of sensitivity analysis methods, for instance methods which estimate the impact of input parameters on the model output derivatives (Lockwood, 2012), on the model output variance (Saltelli, et al, 2008) or on the probability density function of the model output (Borgonovo, 2006). To ensure that a method is generally suitable for different models and different decision situations, Saltelli and Tarantola (2002) stated that sensitivity analysis methods should be "*global, quantitative and model free*".

While "local" sensitivity analysis methods only consider the model output variation for small variation of the input parameters, in "global" sensitivity analysis a neighbourhood of input parameters with its probability density function can be considered. A "model free" method requires no model properties like linearity or additivity, so it is independent of the kind of model. The former stated methods (derivative-, variance- and density-based) fulfil all three criteria of Saltelli and Tarantola. The most established method is the variance-based method, and therefore its strengths and weaknesses are best known. Therefore, the following approach is based on the variance-based sensitivity analysis method.

2.1 Variance-based Sensitivity Analysis

Variance-based sensitivity analysis measures, how much of the model output variance can be explained by the variation of a model input parameter. Basis for variance-based sensitivity analysis is the high dimensional model representation (HDMR) according to Sobol (Saltelli, et al, 2008). If the model has the form of a squared integrable function, the HDMR states that this function can be decomposed in orthogonal subfunctions, which are only dependent on input parameter subsets. The variance of the model output following also separates in parts, which can be assigned to subsets of input parameters. For an input parameter x_i the main effect sensitivity S_i is the part of the outputs variance, which only can be explained by the variation of this input parameter. The total effect sensitivity S_{T_i} of x_i is the part of the outputs variance, which can be explained by the variation of x_i in combination with other input parameters. The sensitivity indices can be defined as terms of the conditional mean and conditional variance, what is briefly done in the following.

Let f be a generic model $f:(X_1, \dots, X_n) \rightarrow Y$ with random variables $X_i \in [0;1]$ as input and the random variable Y as output. The variance $V(Y)$ of the model output then decomposes to

$$V(Y) = E(V(Y|X_i)) + V(E(Y|X_i)), \quad (1)$$

where $E(Y|X_i)$ denotes the conditional expectation of Y with respect to X_i and $V(Y|X_i)$ the conditional variance of Y with respect to X_i , for further information see e. g. (Saltelli, et al, 2008). With the conditional expectation and variance, the main effect sensitivity S_i and total effect sensitivity S_{T_i} of the random variable X_i is defined as

$$S_i = \frac{V(E(Y|X_i))}{V(Y)} \quad \text{and} \quad S_{T_i} = 1 - \frac{V(E(Y|X_{-i}))}{V(Y)},$$

where $\mathbf{X}_{-i}$ denotes all input random variables aside from X_i . While the main effect represents the direct influence of the i^{th} random variable on Y , the total effect additionally considers interaction effects of the i^{th} variable with other input variables. Therefore, the total effect always is greater than or equal to the main effect $S_{T_i} \geq S_i$.

For estimating the sensitivity indices, there are two kinds of algorithms available: random number based (Sobol, Jansen) and spectral based (FAST, exFAST, RBD) algorithms (Saltelli, et al, 2008). Usually, spectral algorithms are more efficient and therefore have less computational costs than random number based ones.

2.2 Sensitivity Analysis in Tolerancing

According to Stuppy and Meerkamm (2009), there exist three common methods for sensitivity/contributor analysis (both terms are interchangeable) in tolerancing: Arithmetical contributor analysis, statistical contributor analysis and high-low-median (HLM) sensitivity analysis. All three are basis for sensitivity analysis in commercial tolerance software. However, these are local sensitivity analysis methods, so they do not fulfil the requirements of Saltelli for sensitivity analysis methods.

Furthermore, there exist only a few publications about global sensitivity analysis in tolerancing. Wu (1997) analyzed the impact of position tolerances on a functional characteristic. The approach is based on the averaged partial derivatives of polar coordinates for the position of a drill hole axis. However, this approach is limited to position tolerances and cannot be simply extended to other tolerances. Markvoort (2007) proposed to use variance-based sensitivity analysis in tolerancing, where a combination of response surface methods with the eFAST algorithm was preferred. Stockinger, et al, (2011) applied variance-based sensitivity analysis to an analytical expressed deviation model. However, the approach is performed with dimensional tolerances. Walter, et al, (2013) performed variance-based sensitivity analysis for a system in motion to identify interactions between the systems input parameters. However, the approach only considers dimensional tolerances and dynamic quantities and is also limited to the used vectorial tolerancing method. Caniou (2012) additionally showed the practical use of global sensitivity analysis in tolerancing by an analytical expressed deviation model of an electrical pin. Variance-based and density-based sensitivity analysis in this context were compared and the influence of correlated input parameters was discussed. All sensitivity analysis approaches which are referred in this section are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Sensitivity analysis methods in tolerancing

Sensitivity Analysis Methods		Quantitative	Global	Model free*
In Commercial Software	High-Low-Median	Yes	No	No
	Arithmetic Contributor	Yes	No	No
	Statistical Contributor	Yes	No	No
In Scientific Publications	Derivative-based	Yes	Yes	No
	Variance-based	Yes	Yes	No
	Density-based	Yes	Yes	No
Variance-based with Deviation Characteristic		Yes	Yes	Yes

*For Tolerance Simulations, model free implies “independent of the deviation representation model”

2.2.1 The need for model free Sensitivity Analysis in Tolerancing

According to Wartzack, et al, (2011), the whole product lifecycle should be integrated into tolerance simulations. During the product development process the information about manufacturing and assembly processes steadily increases. This leads to an increasing complexity of tolerance simulations during the product development process, what may lead to a switch of the mathematical deviation representation. Following, the parameters which represent the geometrical deviations can change. In this context, sensitivity analysis results based on the deviation parameters of the tolerance simulation cannot be compared easily. Therefore, the former described global sensitivity analysis approaches in tolerancing are not model free in the sense, that they are not *independent of the deviation representation model*. A solution of this problem for assemblability studies is the model free sensitivity analysis approach based on the deviation characteristic (Ziegler and Wartzack, 2014).

2.3 Sensitivity Analysis based on the Deviation Characteristic

Framework for sensitivity analysis in this paper is to “*change the tolerance values, while all other conditions remain unchanged*” (e. g. the nominal geometry, the tolerance scheme, process parameters, etc.). Following, sensitivity analysis has to measure the connection between tolerance values and the FKC, while the influence of the kind of deviations indirectly is measured by the sensitivity indices of the tolerances (see Figure 1). For deviation representation models like Tolerance-Map® or Deviation Domain (Ameta, et al, 2011) or discrete deviation representation models based on Skin Model Shapes (Schleich, et al, 2014), consequently the parameters which control the deviating geometry are not considered by the sensitivity analysis.

Figure 1. Sensitivity analysis process based on the deviation characteristic. The sensitivity analysis algorithm is “blind” for the simulation details, it only perceives the deviation characteristics and the measured FKCs.

2.3.1 Deviation Characteristic

Let f be a feature with an associated tolerance with tolerance value t . Let f_d be the mathematical representation for the manufactured feature which is associated with f . For the tolerance value t' which f_d just fulfils, the deviation characteristic is

$$\lambda_t(f_d) = \frac{t'}{t}. \quad (2)$$

In Figure 2, the deviation characteristic λ_t for a deviating line is shown. The deviation characteristic 0.5 indicates, that the deviated line would fulfil a tolerance with the half tolerance value of t .

Figure 2. Tolerated line, associated deviated line and deviation characteristic.

The sensitivity analysis method then measures the relationship between the deviation characteristics of all adopted tolerances and the functional characteristics (Figure 1). The chosen deviation representation model and the virtual assembly representation is concealed for the sensitivity analysis algorithm. Therefore, the proposed sensitivity analysis method is independent from the chosen tolerance simulation (and associated parameters) and fulfils the *model free* requirement of Saltelli.

In the following, the Deviation Domain tolerance representation model (Ameta, et al, 2011) is basis for the sensitivity analysis. The model is widely used and capable of representing dimensional and geometric tolerances. The model represents deviating geometry elements (features) as transformation parameters for small displacements of the nominal geometry. A short outline of Deviation Domains with the explicit formulation of the deviation characteristic λ for this model can be found in (Ziegler and Wartzack, 2014).

3. Sensitivity Analysis of Feature Group Tolerances

In specifying the product's tolerances, often groups of features are restricted by one tolerance. This can have manufacturing reasons as for a hole pattern (Figure 3 a) or symmetric reasons as for two holes in a cylinder head for one pin (Figure 3 b). Furthermore, in these cases usually this scheme is invariable and only the tolerance value will be changed.

Figure 3. Examples for feature groups with one tolerance: a) position tolerance of a hole pattern and b) perpendicularity of two hole axes in a symmetric part

However, in a tolerance simulation deviations would be adopted independently on the individual together restricted features. Consequently, common sensitivity analysis would result in sensitivity indices for all deviating geometry elements.

In practice, a tolerance expert would possibly add the sensitivity values of the features together. This is problematic for the sensitivity total indices, because the total sensitivity indices consider interactions between parameters. These interactions would be summed multiple times, so the total effects would be overestimated (for more details see the Appendix). Following, the sensitivity values cannot be added together for tolerances of multiple features.

$$S_{T_i} \neq \sum_{i=1}^n S_{T_i} \text{ for } n \text{ features with } i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \quad (3)$$

Therefore, a possible approach is to define a deviation characteristic for a feature group with respect to the associated tolerance. For coherence with the definition of geometric tolerances, for a together tolerated group of n deviating features $\mathbf{f}_d = (f_d^1, \dots, f_d^n)$, the deviation characteristic λ_i is

$$\lambda_t(\mathbf{f}_d) = \lambda_t(f_d^1, \dots, f_d^n) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} \lambda_t(f_d^i). \quad (4)$$

The deviation characteristic of a feature group can be formulated as the *maximal ratio of the tolerance value, for which all deviating features would be inside the associated tolerance zones*. An example can be seen in Figure 4, where a deviation characteristic of the axes from Figure 4 b) is shown. For both manufactured holes, the associated axes and their perpendicularity with respect to the datum A are measured. The maximum of both deviation characteristics is the deviation characteristic $\lambda_t = 0.8$ of the left axis, which is the quality of the together restricted feature group (f^1, f^2) , where f^1 is the left axis and f^2 the right axis.

With this deviation characteristic, a FKC which is defined for a feature group can be measured. However, this measure also can be used for defining a sampling for the sensitivity analysis method. Thereby, the more uncertainty in the model is present, the more features and associated model parameters are evaluated together by the deviation characteristic. The dimensionality of these “hidden” parameters of the simulation is therefore not observed by the sensitivity analysis.

Figure 4. Exemplary deviation characteristic of the axes from Figure 3 b)

This is problematic if the “curse of dimensionality” appears. This term designates the phenomenon that analysis methods which require statistical significance become problems with rising dimensionality of the analysed model. This effect can also occur for the proposed model. In addition to the deviation parameters of the geometry, clearance deviations (not uniqueness of relative part positions due to clearance between the parts) can favour the appearance of the phenomenon. As the parameters which are responsible for the curse of dimensionality are hidden for the sensitivity analysis algorithm, the phenomenon is called “hidden” curse of dimensionality here. To reduce this effect, a simple and efficient countermeasure is presented in the following.

3.1 Avoiding the “Hidden” Curse of Dimensionality through coupled Deviation Characteristics

For reducing the unknown uncertainty of the model, one possibility is to reduce the number of free parameters of the simulation model. For this parameter reduction, global sensitivity analysis methods can also be used (Saltelli, et al, 2008). However, this can change the sensitivity analysis results if the fixed parameters are important. A model independent possibility is to couple all deviation characteristics of features which are restricted together by a tolerance, thus

$$\lambda_t(f_d) = \lambda_t(f_d^1) = \lambda_t(f_d^2) = \dots = \lambda_t(f_d^n), \quad (5)$$

in contrast to (4). This definition can be formulated following: *For generating a virtual set of jointly restricted deviating features, all deviating features have the same deviation quality but differ in the manifestation of the deviation.* An example for the part from Figure 3b) can be seen in Figure 5. The two generated deviating axes have the same deviation characteristic 0.8, but the manifestation of the deviation (in which direction the axes are tipped) can vary.

This approach reduces the number of free parameters significant and also if it has influence on the sensitivity analysis results, all considered features in the simulation still can vary. They just *vary together*, which means that all deviating features would hold the same tolerance value. Therefore interaction effects caused by the kind of deviations are still considered, only interactions caused by different deviation qualities are neglected. This is important, as the proposed sensitivity analysis based on the deviation characteristic has the distinction that a lot of interaction effects appear. In the chosen deviation representation model, for diameter parameters the problem arises that the kind of deviation is directly represented by the deviation characteristic. However, in this case coupled deviation characteristics can be seen as representations of systematic manufacturing errors and are therefore appropriate for feature groups.

Figure 5. Generating two deviating axis for the example of Figure 3b): The deviation quality of the axes is equal, but they can vary in the tipping direction.

4. Application to Hole Pattern Tolerances

For demonstrating the proposed approach, the tolerances of a drill hole pattern are analysed in the following. In Figure 6, the geometry of the two plates and the three pins is shown. The drill holes are restricted by diameter tolerances and position tolerances for their axis. The pins have dimensional tolerances. Table 2 lists the tolerances with associated tolerance values. The diameter tolerances for the drill holes as well as the position tolerances for the drill hole axes are assigned for three features together, the pin diameter also is assigned for three pins. Aim of the tolerance expert is to reduce clearance between the two plates.

Note, that if the decision situation would not be considered and sensitivity analysis would be performed for every simulation parameter, there would be 21 sensitivity main and total indices. Additionally to the former discussed problems for decision making this would lead to higher estimation errors in the results.

Table 2. Tolerances of the application example

Tolerance	Part	Tolerance type	Tolerance value
t_d^u	upper plate	dimensional	0.3 mm
t_p^u	"	position	0.2 mm
t_d^l	lower plate	dimensional	0.3 mm
t_p^l	"	position	0.2 mm
t_d^p	pin	dimensional	0.3 mm

The functional key characteristic is the relative position of the upper plate with respect to the lower plate. Therefore, according to (Ziegler and Wartzack, 2014) the relative clearance domain volume of the upper plate with respect to the lower plate is defined as the output parameter of the assembly. The relative clearance domain volume is a parameter of higher order, which considers all translational and rotational deviations of a clearance together. The constraints for relative positions of the upper plate with respect to the lower plate can be formulated as

$$\text{distance}(\mathbf{a}_i^u - \mathbf{a}_i^l) \leq \frac{d_i^l + d_i^u}{2} - d_i^p, \quad (6)$$

where i is the index of the pin-hole connection, $\mathbf{a}_i^{u/l}$ the axis of the i -th upper/lower hole and $d_i^{l/u/p}$ the diameter of the i -th upper plate hole/lower plate hole/pin. The geometrical context of formula (6) can be seen in Figure 6 (lower right) – the distance between the axes of the upper and the lower plate holes, which are connected by a pin, should be less or equal to the difference between the average of both hole diameters and the pin diameter. If this constraint holds, the pin fits in both holes.

Figure 6. Considered tolerances of plates and pins (left), assembly (upper right) and geometrical context of constraint (6) (lower right)

The simulation was performed for 10,000 samples with sobol's sequence, a quasi monte carlo sampling (Saltelli, et al, 2008). The deviation characteristics were sampled from an uniform distribution. The relative clearance domain volume, measure for all possible positions of the upper plate with respect to the lower plate, was estimated with a Monte Carlo filtering with 200 samples, from which 14 hit the clearance domain in nominal position.

Figure 7 shows the kernel density estimation of the relative clearance domain volume. There are no Monte Carlo samples with relative clearance domain volume zero, so all assemblies have clearance. Therefore, the second condition from (Ziegler and Wartzack, 2014) – a small number of unmountable assemblies – is met and the sensitivity analysis method can be performed.

Figure 7. Kernel density estimation of the relative clearance domain volume

In Figure 8 the sensitivity indices for the five tolerances are shown. The sensitivity analysis showed small estimation errors already for 10,000 samples. As there are just little interaction effects between the tolerances, the relations between tolerances and FKC are nearly additive. The position tolerances have the lowest influence on the clearance. It is noticeable, that the pins diameter tolerance has significant higher influence as the diameter tolerances of the hole patterns. This can be explained with equation (6), where the hole pattern diameters are only considered with their half value, while the pin diameter is considered with full value. Resulting it can be stated, that for reducing the clearance, the pin diameter should be tolerated stricter.

Figure 8. Sensitivity analysis results for the hole pattern and pin tolerances

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Basis for this paper was the situation that a tolerance restricts multiple similar features. The problem was displayed, that common global sensitivity analysis results cannot be simply added to get a sensitivity value for the feature group. A method to perform sensitivity analysis in this case was introduced and its practical use was shown for a drill hole pattern. The method is model free, which means it is “independent of the deviation representation model” (like Deviation Domain or Skin Model Shape). With the coupling of the deviation characteristics, the dimensionality of the input parameter space can be reduced. However, the proposed method is just a first step towards a better consideration of the tolerancing decision situation in sensitivity analysis.

Appendix

Originating from the HDMR, the variance $V(Y)$ of the model output Y can be decomposed in the following way (Saltelli, et al, 2000):

$$V(Y) = V_1 + V_2 + \dots + V_n + V_{12} + V_{13} + \dots + V_{n-1n} + \dots + V_{1\dots n}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

In this formulation, the total effect of the i -th random variable X_i can be expressed as the sum of its subvariances where the i -th index is considered

$$S_{T_i} = \frac{\sum_{I \in I} V_I}{V(Y)} \text{ where } I \subset \{1, \dots, n\}. \quad (\text{A2})$$

If for two parameters i and j the total effects are summed, their interaction terms are considered several times:

$$S_{T_i} + S_{T_j} = \frac{\sum_{I \in I} V_I}{V(Y)} + \frac{\sum_{J \in J} V_J}{V(Y)} = \frac{\sum_{\{i\} \cup \{j\} \subset I} V_I}{V(Y)} + \frac{\sum_{\{i,j\} \subset I} V_I}{V(Y)} = S_{T_{ij}} + \frac{\sum_{\{i,j\} \subset I} V_I}{V(Y)} \geq S_{T_{ij}}. \quad (\text{A3})$$

Following, the total effects can only be added if the second term in (A3) (3rd term) becomes zero, what is only the case if there are no interaction effects of the i -th and j -th parameters. The simple application example in (Ziegler and Wartzack, 2014) already showed significant interaction effects, so the interaction terms generally cannot be neglected if sensitivity analysis based on the deviation characteristic is performed.

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